

INVESTIGATING SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, AND RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract

The study offers a concise examination spanning the years 2008 to 2018, focusing on research, professional, technology, and administrative activities within select regions of the European Union characterized by mountainous terrain. These sectors play a pivotal role in supporting the expansive scientific and research infrastructure within the community. The initiatives in research, professional engagement, technology, and administration are strategically devised to enhance the employment landscape, aiming at both quantitative and qualitative improvements to foster increased prosperity and elevate the overall quality of life.

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The manuscript provides a concise overview of Research, professional, technology, and administrative activities within the context of the European Union's mountainous landscapes. Despite the EU's global technological leadership, it grapples with challenges arising from both traditional competitors and emerging economies in the global market. Notably, European companies lag in research and development across key high-tech sectors compared to their counterparts in the United States. The EU's scientific productivity is globally recognized, yet there is a call for more areas of world-class excellence to foster revolutionary results and structural change. The responsibility for building a competitive scientific base rests primarily with member states, and EU support is deemed valuable, particularly through initiatives like the European Research Area. The Common Strategic Framework's funding is crucial in propelling progress towards a unified ERA.

Research and development programs within the EU, coupled with Romania's policies on research, development, and innovation, aim to foster collaboration between various entities to stimulate consortia involvement.

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European policies on participation in science and technology have evolved through distinct phases, emphasizing deliberation, transitioning to innovation, and currently focusing on participation in knowledge and innovation production.

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At the EU level, Big Science and Research Infrastructures are integral components with frameworks encompassing intergovernmental cooperation, pan-European policies outlined in the ESFRI roadmap, and national paths aligned with European interests. This complex framework emphasizes science integration based on "interdependence" and "politicization."

Science and technology within the EU are intricately linked to administrative activities. The political control of knowledge has been a strategic concern throughout history, particularly evident in the contemporary era's shift towards post-industrialism and the knowledge society. The EU, recognizing the need for restructuring its economy, education system, and social security, faces increasing competition from Asian science and technology sectors.

In the realm of mountain science, technology, professionals, and administrative sectors, statistics reveal positive trends over the past decade.

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Mean values for these sectors across various countries, including Bulgaria, Italy, Austria, Portugal, Romania, and Slovakia, exhibit continuous growth. The accompanying histograms illustrate distribution curves, showcasing distinct patterns for Italy, Slovakia, Portugal, Austria, Bulgaria, and Romania in the context of science, technology, professionals, and administrative activities within the mountain sector.

Figure 1. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities - Bulgaria

Figure 2. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities - Italy

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Figure 3. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Austria

Figure 4. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Portugal

Figure 5. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Romania

Figure 6. Histogram for Professional, scientific and technical activities;
administrative and support activities - Slovakia

The initial cluster of nations, encompassing Italy and Slovakia, exhibits a persistent upward trajectory in activities, while Portugal demonstrates a gradual decline. In contrast, the second cluster comprising Austria, Bulgaria, and Romania experiences a significant increase.

The overarching trend within this sector during the scrutinized period indicates a rise in the population of active enterprises within the European mountain economy of the studied sector from 2008 to 2018. The scrutinized timeframe highlights a discernible intensification of activity. The statistical data provided earlier, along with the accompanying histogram, substantiate the notable agglomeration and developmental pattern within this sector in mountainous Europe. Simultaneously, the statistics affirm the heightened growth rate characterizing this sector, suggesting its potential as one of the most valuable components for mountainous Europe.

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